

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343222306>

Prevalence of Educational Adjustment Disorder among Pre-NCE Students in Federal College of Education Kano

Article · July 2020

CITATIONS

0

READS

227

2 authors:

Abubakar Sadiq Haruna
Federal University, Gusau

38 PUBLICATIONS 64 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Umar Hassan
Ahmadu Bello University

12 PUBLICATIONS 3 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Prevalence of Educational Adjustment Disorder among Pre-NCE Students in Federal College of Education Kano

Abubakar Sadiq Haruna

Department of Psychology and Counselling
Federal College of Education, Kano
drashm72@gmail.com

&

Umar Hassan

Department of General Studies
Kano State Polytechnic
umarhas@yahoo.com

Abstract

This study investigated prevalence of Educational Adjustment Disorder among Pre-NCE students in Federal College of Education, Kano. To achieve this, cross-sectional survey was employed in which 322 participants were proportionally sampled from a cumulative population of 1,930 Pre-NCE students in Federal College of Education (FCE), Kano. Three research questions with corresponding hypotheses were postulated and tested. Data used for hypotheses testing was obtained through a scale developed by the researchers called Educational Adjustment Disorder Assessment Scale (EADAS) whose reliability of 0.74 was estimated via Cronbach's Alpha procedure. Percentage of the distribution of cases of Educational Adjustment Disorder (EAD) was computed and used to answer the research questions. Whereas, One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) Z-score procedure was used to test H_{01} , t-test and chi-square were employed to analyze H_{02} and H_{03} respectively at 0.05 confidence level. Results obtained from the analysis revealed that; whereas 27.6% of participants had EAD, highest cases (30% of the respondents) are in school of Arts and Social Sciences. Similarly, female students recorded 55% incidence while their male counterparts had 45%. Also, prevalence of EAD was found to be significant (Z-score = - 48.63 at $P < 0.05$). As for gender and level differentials in the prevalence of EAD, no significant difference was found between male and female students and among the five schools. A major recommendation offered suggests that; psycho-educational intervention should be used by psychologists to assist students with symptoms of EAD.

Keywords: Prevalence, Educational Adjustment Disorder, Pre-NCE students

Introduction

The environment in which students of pre-Nigeria Certificate in Education (Pre-NCE) learn is characterized by stress, trauma, anxiety and other related psychological variables that are necessary for learning. These variables are potential impediments to students' adjustment in school settings. While some are able to overcome the problems, many find it difficult to cope with them. Pre-NCE is a one-year course that prepares students for admission into the Nigeria Certificate in Education programme. As a remedial course, many of the students admitted into the programme are those who could not gain admission into the NCE courses, which may partly be due to deficiencies in their Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) results. Such deficiencies may be attributed to some differential difficulties in cognitive processing that are fundamental to learning (Crouse, 2010), such as Attention Deficit Disorders (ADD) and general educational maladjustment (stigma due to parental poverty, retarded intellectual ability, insult and corporal punishment etc).

Apart from the stressors (triggers of stress) of passing and qualifying for admission into NCE programme, Pre-NCE students are embodied with the stress of sitting and passing the JAMB exams with a result of not less than 160 points. More so, population explosion in classrooms (a stressor)

does not only undermine the efforts of teachers in caring for individual differences, but complicates learning process (Haruna, 2008). Thus, students with adjustment difficulties are left to struggle with the challenges of adjusting to learning environment (Odogwu, 2008). And if such challenges persist for more than three months, may lead to Adjustment Disorder (Dontel, 2017).

National Institute of Mental Health (2015) opined that adjustment disorder is a change or regression in behaviour or emotion in response to a specific environmental change. This implies that individual struggling with disorder normally respond to the stress in a way that is excessive when compared to what was normal to that individual. In the same vain, Dontel (2017) maintains that adjustment disorder is stress-related. In other words, strong and long lasting reaction to an upsetting event might cause adjustment disorder. Such events might be a death of a family member, parental divorce, excessive labour, accumulated daily hassles like traffic jam, interruptive sleep delayed meals, (Sara, 2017). Erica (2016) View adjustment disorder as a “temporary condition caused by stress which is linked with psychological and sometimes physical symptoms that can interfere with ones' everyday life.”

In educational settings however, adjustment is often a difficult task to some students (Haruna, 2016). Although, most individuals are able to adjust to change in school settings within a few months, those with adjustment disorder continue to feel sad and self-destructive, and may become overwhelmed with their daily routines and make reckless decision that can lead to serious consequences, such as dropping out from the school, suicidal thought (Haruna, 2015). The persistence of such behaviours among students in educational environment that is often referred to as Educational Adjustment Disorder (EAD).

Some of the signs of educational adjustment disorder as stated by Dontal (2017) include but not limited to lack of enjoyment, trouble sleeping, difficulty to concentrate, worry, anxiety, fighting, poor performance in school, skipping school, vandalizing school properties, socially withdrawn from family and friends etc thus educational adjustment disorder can affect all areas of individual life.

Adjustment disorder is of several types. Erica (2016) identified six types of adjustment disorder; the first type is adjustment disorder with depressed mood in which an individual tend to experience feeling of sadness and hopelessness, it is also associated with crying and individual with this type of disorder will no longer enjoy activities that he formally enjoyed. Secondly, adjustment disorder with anxiety which include feeling overwhelmed, anxious and worried, people with this disorder may also have problem with concentration and memory, it is usually associated with separation anxiety from parent and loved ones. The third one is adjustment disorder with mix anxiety and depression, in which people experiences both depression and anxiety. Erica (2016) also identified the fourth type as adjustment disorder with disturbance of conduct. Symptoms of this disorder mainly involved behavioral issues like driving recklessly, starting fighting, stealing, vandalizing of property as well as missing school. The fifth type is adjustment disorder with mixed disturbance of emotion and conduct. This includes depression, anxiety and behavioral problems. Finally, is adjustment disorder unspecified, people with this have symptoms that are not associated with the other types of disorder, this often include physical symptoms or problems with friends, family work or school.

Several theoretical postulations have established basis for adjustment disorder. For instance, Joseph and Linelys (2005) in their organismic valuing theory of growth through adversity emphasis on intrinsic motivation toward growth, that leads to the state of intrusion and avoidance. The theory identifies three possible outcome of cognitive-emotional processing as inducers of psychological wellbeing, namely; assimilation, negative accommodation and positive accommodation (Joseph & Linelys, 2005). The theory explains how organismic valuing process will automatically lead to actualization of positive changes in psychological well-being , through the positive accommodation of the new trauma related information , provided that the social environment is able to support this positive accommodation process.

Another theory of adjustment disorder is the cognitive adaptation by Tylor (1983). He argued that the adjustment process centers on three theme; a search for meaning in the experience, an attempt to regain mastery over the event in particular and an effort to restore self-esteem through self-

enhancing evaluations. The theory maintained that successful adjustment depends, in a large part on ability to sustain and modify illusion that buffer not only against the present threat but against possible future set back.

Studies conducted on adjustment disorder have revealed significant findings. The study by Asani, Farouk and Gambo (2016) on prevalence of perceived stress among clinical students of Bayero University, Kano employed a cross-sectional study. They used Cohen's perceived stress scale to access the severity of stress among students. Results of their study show a prevalence of 59.8%. No gender differential was however revealed. Although findings by Asani and associates do not directly corroborate with the present study, the variable investigated is relatively relevant to the problem under study.

Abdullahi (2016) studied the influence of traumatic stress on academic adjustment among tertiary institution students in Potiskum, Yobe State. In the study, ex-post factor design was employed and 364 students were sampled from 6767 population. Results show a significant gender difference in traumatic stress exists. It also reveals that academic adjustment does not differ among students with traumatic stress. Study by Abdullahi does reveal the interplay of some indicators of adjustment disorder as trauma and stress are features that most often prevail among students with EAD.

A closely related study conducted by Haruna (2016) on prevalence of stress and attention disorder among pre-NCE students in Federal College of Education, Kano reveals significant findings. The main objectives of the study were to find out the prevalence of stress; determine the association between stress and ADD and reveal gender difference in the prevalence of ADD among stressed pre-NCE students. Cross-Sectional Correlation Design was employed in which 333 (Male = 65%; Female = 35%) students were proportionately sampled and administered Stress Assessment Scale [SAS $r=0.74$] and those identified with stress were thereafter rated with Cognitive Processing Inventory [CPI], Results revealed significant prevalence of stress [Z -calculated = 2.24; Z -critical= ± 1.96], and a positive relationship between Stress and ADD among Pre-NCE students [r -calculated = 0.450; r -critical = 0.138]. However, there was no gender difference in the prevalence of ADD among stressed Pre-NCE students in the college [t -calculated = 1.49; t -critical = 1.645]. The study concludes that while stress and ADD are positively associated, there was no gender difference in the prevalence of ADD among stressed pre-NCE students. The significant of the study by Haruna is that, both stress and ADD are sub-units of educational adjustment disorder.

A cross-sectional study by Koochaki, Charkazi, Hasanzadeh, Saedani, Qorbani & Marjani, (2010) measured the frequency of self-reported stress symptoms among a weighted random sample of medical students in Isfahan, Islamic Republic of Iran. The data were gathered using the Kessler 10-item psychological distress scale. The overall prevalence of stress among 222 students was 61.3% and there were no statistically significant differences in stress levels between students in the pre-clinical and clinical phases or different years of study. Married students had significantly lower scores than single students but there were no differences between the sexes. Students who chose to study medicine had lower stress scores than those who were influenced by family or had no choice about the subject. Students with mild to moderate stress were significantly more likely to suffer physical problems (OR = 4.42). Significant issues established by Koochaki and associates' study are that; stress as a psychological factor of adjustment can make individual suffer physical problem which is a very critical symptom that persists among students with educational adjustment disorder.

Review of studies presented above have depict that most (Asani, Farouk & Gambo, 2016; Abdullahi, 2016; & Haruna, 2016) of the researches conducted focused on some indicators of educational adjustment disorder, such as stress, attention deficit disorder, traumatic disorder. Although, some of the studies that reflected on EAD were foreign based, none adequately addressed its prevalence among pre-NCE students in Federal College of Education, Kano. The present study is designed to bridge the gap. Therefore the thrust of the study is to investigate the prevalence of Educational Adjustment Disorder among pre-NCE students in Federal College of Education, Kano. To achieve this purpose, three objectives along with three research questions and corresponding hypotheses were postulated as follows:

Objectives of the Study

1. To establish the prevalence of Educational Adjustment Disorder among pre-NCE students in Federal College of Education, Kano;
2. To determine difference in Educational Adjustment Disorder between male and female pre-NCE students in FCE Kano;
3. To reveal difference in the prevalence of Educational Adjustment Disorders among students in the five schools running pre-NCE programme in Federal College of Education, Kano.

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant prevalence of Educational Adjustment Disorder among pre-NCE students in Federal College of Education Kano.
2. There is no significant difference in the prevalence of Educational Adjustment Disorder between male and female pre-NCE students in the college.
3. There is no significant difference in the prevalence of Educational Adjustment Disorder among students in the five schools running pre-NCE programme in FCE Kano.

Research Methodology

Cross-sectional Survey design was employed, thus data was collected from a representative sample of the population (Haruna, 2012). To achieve this, the entire population (Pre - NCE students) was sorted into five (school system) sections and samples were selected from the cross - section. This ensured a comprehensive study of a problem within a distinct population (Pre - NCE students, FCE Kano), over a short period of time. The population of the study was 1,930. That is 926 (48%) male and 1,004 (52%) female Pre-NCE (2015/2016 session) students in the five schools of the college (Federal College of Education, Kano 2017).

Table 1: Population of the study (N = 1, 930)

School	Male	Female	Total
Arts & Social Sciences	257	278	535
ECCE & PES	167	180	347
Languages	238	259	497
Sciences	166	180	346
Vocational Education	98	107	205
Total	926	1,004	1,930
%	48	52	100

Academic Records Office, FCE, Kano, 2015/2016 session

In line with appropriate procedure for sample size as recommended by The Research Advisors (2006), a total of 322 participants were proportionally drawn following Simple Stratified Random Sampling technique. This technique was employed in other to ensure representativeness of the samples (Olayiwola, 2008).

Table 2: Sample size (n = 322)

School	Male	Female	Total
Arts & Social Sciences	43	46	89
ECCE & PES	28	30	58
Languages	40	43	83
Sciences	28	30	58
Vocational Education	16	18	34
Total	155	167	322
%	48	52	100

Academic Records Office, FCE, Kano, 2015/2016 session

Guided by the distribution in Table 2, random sampling was used to select participants from each stratum. Since the study required a thorough understanding of adjustment disorder among participants, 10 students (5 males & 5 females) were engaged as Research Assistants. The Assistants

were trained on the rudiments of the exercise, such as administration and scoring of data collection instrument. Participants' consent was sought through their respective Heads of Department.

The instrument used for data collection was an Educational Adjustment Disorder Assessment Scale (EADAS) (developed by the researchers) whose reliability coefficient measured via Cronbach alpha was 0.74. Content validity for EADAS was demonstrated by examining the consistency of the inventory with research and theoretical literature as well as assessment by experts. Research Assistants have been trained on usage of the inventory, administered it on participants. A total of 322 EADAS copies were given to the Research Assistants to enable them carry out the rating exercise. Extra copies of the inventory were also provided for rerating/replacement of damaged scale where necessary. In a nutshell, a four week period was earmarked for data collection.

Results

Data obtained via the completed scale was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version- 17.0 software) to determine participants' adjustment disorder. One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) Z-score procedure was used to test null hypothesis 1, (H_01) whereas, t-test was employed to analyze H_02 , chi-square statistic was applied on H_03 . A total of 89 cases (27.6%) of BAD were recorded through assessment of students, Table 3 shows summary of the assessment.

Table 3: A Summary of assessment of students with EAD (n=89)

School	Male	Female	Total
Arts & Social Sciences	10 (11.2%)	17 (19.1%)	27 (30.3%)
ECCE & PES	05 (5.6%)	06 (6.7%)	11 (12.3%)
Languages	12 (13.5%)	10 (11.2%)	22 (24.7%)
Sciences	06 (6.8%)	09 (10.1%)	15 (16.9%)
Vocational Education	07 (7.9%)	07 (7.9%)	14 (15.8%)
Total	40 (45%)	49 (55%)	89 (100%)
%	48	52	100

Data on Table 3 shows the frequencies and percentages of Educational Adjustment Disorder across five schools and between genders. School of Arts and Social Sciences records highest cases (30.3%) while school of Vocational Education had 15.8% of the cases. Similarly, female students had 55% incidence while their male counterparts recorded 45%.

H_01 : There is no significant prevalence of Educational Adjustment Disorder among pre- NCE students in Federal College of Education Kano.

This hypothesis was analyzed using one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) Z-score procedure and result is presented in table 4 below:

Table 4: Z-Score calculation significant prevalence of Adjustment Disorder

Parameters	Values
Population Size	1, 930
Population Mean	386
Population Variance	14080.8
Sample Size	322
Sample Mean	64.4
Z-score	-48.63
P-Value	0.000
Decision	Reject H_01

The above statistics in Table 4 show calculated Z-Score for the significant prevalence of Educational Adjustment Disorder among pre-NCE students in FCE, Kano. The Z-score of -48.63 is significant at P-value of 0.000 less than the threshold (0.05). Therefore, null hypothesis 1 is hereby

rejected. This implies that, there is a significant prevalence of Educational Adjustment Disorders among pre-NCE students in FCE Kano.

H₀₂: There is no significant gender difference in Educational Adjustment Disorder among pre-NCE students in FCE Kano.

To test this hypothesis, two tailed t-test was employed at 0.05 level of significance and result is presented in table 5 below:

Table 5: t-test analysis for gender difference

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Male	40	8.0	2.9	87	-0.77	0.462	Retain H ₀₃
Female	49	9.8	4.3				

Figures presented in Table 5 reveal that P-value of 0.462 is greater than the threshold of 0.05 probability. Therefore null hypothesis 2 is retained.

H₀₃

There is no significant difference in the prevalence of Adjustment Disorder among students in the five schools running pre-NCE programme in FCE Kano.

To analyze this hypothesis, a 5X5 contingency Chi-Square was used and result obtained is presented in table 6 below:

Table 6: Chi-Square statistic on difference in prevalence of EAD among schools

Schools	Male Category	Female Category
Arts & Social Sciences	10 (12.13) [0.38]	17 (14.87) [0.31]
ECCE & PES	5 (4.94) [0.00]	6 (6.06) [0.00]
Languages	12 (9.89) [0.45]	10 (12.11) [0.37]
Sciences	6 (6.74) [0.08]	9 (8.26) [0.07]
Vocational Education	7 (6.29) [0.08]	7 (7.71) [0.07]
Column Total	40	49

*Chi-square statistic is 1.7958. The *p*-value is .773252. Result is not significant at *p* < .05

The chi-square statistics on table 6 above did not reveal significant difference in prevalence of Educational Adjustment Disorder among students in the five schools in FCE, Kano. Figures in the table show that the chi-value of 1.7958 is not significant (P-value: 0.773252) at 0.05 probability threshold. Therefore, the postulated null hypothesis 3 is hereby retained.

Discussion of Findings

Analysis of data obtained via EADAS has revealed significant results. Finding on the first hypothesis indicates that calculated Z-Score for the prevalence of Educational Adjustment Disorder among pre-NCE students in FCE, Kano (-48.63) is significant at P-value of 0.000 less than the threshold (0.05). It shows that 27.6% of the participants assessed had educational adjustment disorder. This result corroborates study by Asani, Farouk and Gambo (2016) on prevalence of perceived stress among clinical students of Bayero University, Kano. They used Cohen's perceived stress scale to assess the severity of stress among students. Results of their study show a prevalence of 59.8%. Although variables investigated by Asani and associates differ from the present study, they are however sub-units of the problem studied. Similarly, Abdullahi (2016) examined the influence of traumatic stress on academic adjustment among tertiary institution students in Potiskum, Yobe State and found a positive association between academic adjustment and traumatic stress. Study by Abdullahi does reveal the interplay of some indicators of adjustment disorder as trauma and stress are features that most often prevail among students with EAD. Although, his study is limited to association between academic adjustment and a potential indicator (traumatic stress) of adjustment disorder, such relationship could signify likelihood of the problem. Also, in Haruna's study of 2016 on prevalence of stress and attention deficit disorder, results revealed significant prevalence of stress [Z-calculated = 2.24; Z~critical = ±1.96], and a positive relationship between Stress and ADD among

Pre-NCE students [r -calculated =0.450; r -critical =0.138]. This research further vindicates the present study on the fact both stress and ADD are features of EAD.

Finding obtained from analysis of the second hypothesis on gender difference in prevalence of BAD reveals that P-value of 0.462 is greater than the threshold of 0.05 probability. This statistics support the postulated null hypothesis which says that males and females do not differ in the prevalence of educational adjustment disorder. This finding is similar to that of Abdulahi (2016) who studied the influence of traumatic stress on academic adjustment among tertiary institution students in Potiskum, Yobe State. In the study, ex-post factor design was employed and 364 students were sampled from 6767 population. Result shows a significant gender difference in traumatic stress. A related study by Haruna (2016) shows that there was no gender difference in the prevalence of ADD among stressed (potential features of BAD) pre-NCE students. This was confirmed by Asani, Farouk and Gambo (2016) in their study on prevalence of perceived stress among clinical students of Bayero University, Kano. They found no difference between males and females in prevalence of stress.

The chi-square analysis on the third hypothesis does not show any significant difference in prevalence of Educational Adjustment Disorder among students in the five schools in FCE, Kano. Figures in the table reveal that the chi-value of 9.9504 is not significant (P-value: 0.8692) at 0.05 probability threshold. A cross-sectional study by Koochaki, Charkazi, Hasanzadeh, Saedani, Qorbani & Marjani, (2010) supports the present result. Koochaki and associates measured the frequency of self-reported stress symptoms among a weighted random sample of medical students in Isfahan, Islamic Republic of Iran. Data were gathered using the Kessler 10-item psychological distress scale. The overall prevalence of stress among 222 students was 61.3% and there were no statistically significant differences in stress levels between students in the pre-clinical and clinical phases or different years of study. Students with mild to moderate stress were significantly more likely to suffer physical problems (OR = 4.42).

Conclusion

Educational Adjustment Disorder no doubt is one of the psychological issues relating to students life and successes in school. The prevalence of the problem in Federal College of Education, Kano is alarming. The disorder may show up in different forms; either as a specific problem (stress, emotional, anxiety, underachievement etc.), or may occur as a combination of two or more psychological problems. What is significant about EAD is that it has the potential of distorting the entire life of students. Finally this paper posits that despite normal challenges and day to day pressure of life that go with an ever dynamic society and social structure as manifested in the recent serious security situation in Nigeria, the rather enduring economic recession, increasing rate of urban-rural migration may lead to educational adjustment disorder among students in Nigeria, Therefore appropriate therapeutical intervention is require in order to assist students with symptoms of the disorder.

Recommendations

Based on the findings obtained from the present study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Psycho-educational intervention should be employed by psychologists in the Guidance and Counselling center of the College to assist students with symptoms of EAD. This would help them to self-explore their difficulties and identify viable management strategies for their problem.
2. School counsellors and psychologists should employ stress management techniques/ program aimed at reducing potential stressors that can lead adjustment difficulties.
3. Guidance and counselling center of the college should mentoring programme for students with persistent educational disorder so that they can gain from skills and the life experiences of their mentors who have a lot experience in life hassles.

References

Abdullahi, U, (2016). *Influence of traumatic stress on academic adjustment among tertiary institutions students in Potiskum, Yobe State*. Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria: M.Ed. Thesis.

- Asani, M. O., Farouk, 2. & Gambo, S. (2016). *Prevalence of perceived stress among clinical students of Bayero University, Kano Medical School*. Retrieved October 22, 2017 from <http://www.nibc5net./text.asp?2016/13/I/55/176209>
- Crouse, S. L. (2010). *Cognitive Processing Inventory*. Available at <http://www.LDinfo,htra>
- DonteJ. J, (2017). *Teen and adolescent adjustment disorder treatment*. Retrieved October 21, 2017 from <http://www.villagebh.cQm/d?'sorders/adiustmentdisorder>
- Erica, U. (2016). *Adjustment disorder: types, causes and symptoms*. Retrieved October 21, 2017 from <https://www.healthline.com/health/adjustment-disorder#causes4>
- Haruna, A. S. (2008). *Cognitive processing weaknesses among demonstration primary school pupils in F.C.E. Kano: a challenge to UBE programme*. A paper presented at the 3rd Annual National Conference of the Association of Nigerian Academics (ANA) held at Federal College of Education Okene, between 21st and 25th April, 2008.
- Haruna, A. S. (2015). Attention deficit disorders among stressed pre-NCE students in Federal College of Education, Kano. *International Science Index* 13 (1), 2182- 2186.
- Haruna, A.S. (2016). Correlates of stress and Attention Deficit Disorders among pre-NCE students in Federal College of Education, Kano. *National Journal of Special Needs Education* 2 (2), 40-48.
- Joseph. S. & Linely, P .A. (2005). Positive adjustment to threatening event; an organismic valuing theory of growth through adversity. *Review of General Psychology* 9(3) 262-280,
- Koochaki GM, Charkazi A, Hasanzadeh A, Saedani M. Qorbani M, Marjani A (2010). Prevalence of stress among medical students in Isfahan, Islamic Republic of Iran. *Psychological Science* 15 (2): 115-118
- National Institute of Mental Health (2015). Retrieved October 15, 2017 from <http://www.nimh.nih.govt>
- Odogwu, N. B. (2008). *Effects of motivation on attention and perception in Mathematics lesson among private primary school pupils in Fagge Local Government of Kano state*. Federal College of Education Kano: Unpublished PGDE Dissertation.
- Olayiwola, A.O. (2008). *Procedures in Educational Research*, Kaduna: Hanijam.
- Research Advisors. (2006). *Sample size table*. Retrieved October 10, 2012 from <http://www.research-advisors.com/tools/samplesize.htm>
- Sara, Y.A. (2016). *Relationship between emotion dysregulation, psychological disorders and academic performance among senior secondary school students in Gwaram Local Government Area, Jigawa state*. A Paper presented at 2016 Annual conference of Nigeria Society for Educational Psychologist held at Imo State University Owerri